

DOES INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY MATTER IN THE FINANCE-ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY NEXUS IN ECOWAS?

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Abstract

This study investigated the role of institutional quality in finance and environmental quality nexus in ECOWAS sub-Region. The study was built on two models. The baseline model is built without interaction terms; while the second model is the outcome of the interaction of financial development (FD) and institutional quality. The researchers adopted cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (CS-ARDL) technique in estimating the results of the models. The conditional impact of financial development on environmental quality (that is when financial development index is interacted with institutional quality index) is negative and significant at the 1% level of significant. This implies that financial development index on its own reduced environmental pollution and the interaction with institutional quality further enhanced the quality of the environment in ECOWAS. The study recommends that ECOWAS sub-Region fostering of efficient and strong institutions in order to achieve a benign environment.

Keywords: Institutional quality, finance, environmental quality, sustainable development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial systems have basic functions, which is to ensure that economic resources are transferred across time, borders and different sectors. A well-developed financial system attracts foreign direct investment (Ang, 2008a) and augments growth. Figure 1 below highlights the defining factors (depth, access and efficiency of financial institutions and markets) of financial development.

Figure 1: Factors defining financial development

Figure 2 below represents domestic credit to private sector of selected ECOWAS countries depicting differences in the level of financial development. As observed in Figure 2, Sierra Leone had relatively low financial development compared to other ECOWAS countries. Surprisingly, Nigeria's financial development is also relatively low despite having large economy. According to Chimere, Simplice, Odo and Ojiem (2020), domestic credit to private sector in South Africa in 2017 stood at 142% while it is 13.03% in Nigeria and 4.85% in Sierra Leone. It is observed that financial sector development in ECOWAS seems to have a regular pattern. 1985 to 2000 is observed to have a downward trend while from 2000 to 2017 had upward trend suggesting improvement in financial development.

Figure 2: Domestic credit to private sector
Source: World Development Indicators, 2019

Evidence has shown that there have been stronger ties and partnerships among countries in terms of cross-border trade and financial linkages now than a couple of decades ago. For instance, global trade openness, which is measured as the sum of exports and imports of goods and services in per cent of global GDP was on average less than 40 per cent in the 1970s, but this has increased to over 55 per cent in the 2010s. Similarly, global financial openness, measured as the sum of foreign assets and liabilities in per cent of GDP, also increased from less than 100 per cent in the 1970s to almost 400 per cent in the 2010s. These stronger linkages evidenced in the Figures 3 and 4 below have also increased the feedback, in both directions, between business cycles in advanced economies and those in emerging and developing economies. They also ultimately raise the odds of more pronounced and more synchronous movements in the global business cycle.

Source: World Bank, 2015

Source: World Bank, 2015

The importance of the above analysis is that in a study of the relationship between financial development and environmental quality, quality of institutions could have some implications. Empirical evidences have shown that a consensus on the impact of financial development on environmental degradation is still inconclusive while the role of institutional quality in this nexus is scarce for ECOWAS. While some studies document that financial development improves the quality of the environment by reducing carbon emissions (Pradeepta, et al, 2020; Yijuan, et al, 2020; Hamisu, et al, 2019), some studies also found that financial development degrades environmental quality (Renaity, et al, 2021;Abbasi & Riaz, 2016; Mohammad, et al, 2015).

Therefore, this study has the following objectives:

- i. To determine the interactive impact of institutional quality and financial development on environmental quality in ECOWAS sub-Region.
- ii. To investigate if there is evidence of N-shaped Environmental Kuznets Curve in ECOWAS sub-Region.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Literature Review

There are two opposing notions respecting the effects of financial development on environmental quality. The first notion is that a well-developed financial system supports growth of borrowing by enterprises to boost further purchases of machines, equipment and increases in energy consumption. Consequently, the higher the energy consumption, the more carbon emissions are released into the air and the more polluted the environment (Chang, 2015). Conversely, financial systems can and do support a friendly environment when new products that are environment-friendly and energy saving are purchased through easy access to loans facilitates. New, modern household appliances and technical devices produce less carbon emissions and may reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions. Therefore, even though financial development (FD) promotes economic growth and development, this could be advantageous or disadvantageous for the environment. For example, FD helps producers buy advanced machinery and equipment by offering cheaper loans, thus, reducing environmental degradation. Additionally, FD could also increase environment-friendly investments by promoting renewable energy sources and efficient technologies and lead to environmental quality (Shahbaz et al., 2016). On the other hand, FD provokes customers to borrow money and buy luxurious products like houses, automobiles, and air conditioners, resulting in environmental pollution (Baloch et al., 2018).

The theoretical expositions above lay credence to the adoption of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory as the theoretical foundation of this paper. The theory predicts an inverted u-shaped curve with a turning point level of income at which people choose to reduce the personal pollution they create or are exposed to. The EKC hypothesis argues that in the first stage of economic development and by extension financial development, the increase of income causes a certain amount of increase in CO₂ emissions. Nevertheless, when economic development reaches a certain threshold, the negative effect of income on pollution turns out to be positive. In other words, any increase in income is associated with a decrease in CO₂ emissions and forms an inverted U-shaped curve. The EKC is vital in the sense that if there is an inverted U-shaped EKC, environmental degradation will stop at some point of economic growth, and environmental quality will become better as economies grow further. In other words, economic activity always generates pollution, and at the beginning of the economic growth, people do not care or have not resolved to

preserve the environment. However, as wealth increases over time, people generally increase spending on pollution reduction.

2.2. Empirical Literature

Financial development and Environmental Quality

Quite a number of empirical researches have been carried out on the nexus between financial development and environmental quality with the findings being inconclusive. This is because, some argue that financial development deteriorates the environment while others established a negative linkage. For example, Shahbaz et al (2013) explored the linkages among financial development, economic growth, energy consumption, trade openness, and CO₂ emissions in Indonesia with data spanning 1975 to 2011 and they found evidence for positive association between economic growth, energy consumption, trade openness and carbon emission. Also their findings showed that financial development exert negative linkage with carbon emission. A similar study in India by Boutabba (2014) revealed a negative association between financial development and carbon emission. Rising literature on environmental economy has established a positive spillover impact of financial development on carbon emission (Xiaoping, Yijun and Feitao, 2019; Caselles and Sanz, 2021; Wen, Song, Yang, and Gao, 2022). Xiaoping, Yijun and Feitao (2019) argued that a well developed financial sector can provide more capital at cheaper cost thereby leading to capital flows into environmental protection and energy-saving projects and companies which will in turn boost the development of environmental protection firms. By so doing, most firms will adopt energy-saving technologies which will lead to reduction of environmental pollution (Zhao, Jiang and Zhang, 2022).

Institutional Quality and Environmental Sustainability

Studies have been channeled in the area of the linkages between institutional quality and environmental quality with conflicting result. For instance, Tamazian and Rao(2010) explored the effect of institutional quality on carbon emission in 24 transition nations with data spanning 1993 to 2004. Adopting GMM techniques, they found positive association between institutional quality and environmental pollution. In a similar study in MENA nations, Goel, Herrala (2013) established a positive linkage between institutional quality and carbon emission. Utilizing panel data spanning from 1987 to 2000 for 94 countries, Cole (2007) validated a positive association between corruption and pollution.

On the contrary, some studies found a negative and significant relationship between institutional quality and environmental pollution. Examples of such studies include: Zakaria and Bibi (2019) for the case of South Asian Nations; Lau and Choong(2014) for the case of Malaysia; Ibrahim and Law (2016) for the case of. Sub Saharan African countries.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Source

Table 1 depicts data sources and measurement.

Table 1: Description of Variables

Variables	Measurement	Sources
Carbon dioxide emissions (CO ₂)	Metric tons per capita	World Bank (WDI) Data
Financial development (FD)	IM F multi -dimensional financial decomposition of financial index measures Financial development	IMF (https://data.imf.org)

Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC)	Constant 2010 US\$	World Bank (WDI) Data
Institutional quality index (INSTQ)	Index of six governance indicators (such as Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law and Control of Corruption)	WGI (www.govindicators.org)
Urbanization (URB)	Urban population (% of total population)	World Bank (WDI) Data
Globalization index (GLO)	KOFI Globalization Index	KOFI

Source: Authors Computation, 2024

3.2. Model specification

Based on the works of Alhassan, et al, (2022); Renaity, et al, (2021); Yijuan, et al (2020), among others, this study presents Carbon emission (CO₂) as a function of financial development (FD), Gross domestic product per capita (GDPC), institutional quality index and a set of control variables (such as Urbanization- URB and globalization-GLO), which could have influence on Financial development-environmental degradation nexus. Thus, our baseline model for our first objective is specified in their logarithm forms:

$$LnCO_{2it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FD_{it} + \alpha_2 lnGDPC_{it} + \alpha_3 INSTQ_{it} + \alpha_4 lnURB_{it} + \alpha_5 lnGlo_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where,

Where i and t signify countries and years, ln represent logarithm values of the variables, μ_{it} is the white noise assumption and other variables remain as explained in table 1.

In order to capture objective two and three, we modify the model to include the squared terms of FD and GDPC as well as interaction term of FD and INSTQ and as such, the new model becomes:

$$LnCO_{2it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FD_{it} + \beta_3 FDsq_{it} + \beta_4 lnGDPC_{it} + \beta_5 lnGDPCsq_{it} + \beta_6 INSTQ_{it} + \beta_7 lnURB_{it} + \beta_8 lnGlo_{it} + \beta_9 FD * INSTQ_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where, FDsq and GDPCsq are the squared terms of FD and GDPC used to validate the EKC hypothesis (which is our second objective), α_0 and β_0 are the intercepts of the two models; $\alpha_1 - \alpha_5$ and $\beta_1 - \beta_8$ = coefficients of the explanatory variables to be estimated; μ_{it} , and ε_{it} denote the stochastic terms, and finally, FD*INSTQ is the interaction term used to establish the role of institutional quality when mixed with financial development (this is the third objective).

Following the EKC hypothesis, as the economy grows and by extension financial development, this could cause CO₂ emissions to increase. However, after a certain threshold, increase in income and financial development is expected to have reducing impact on carbon 2 emission. This gives rise to environmental degradation taking U-shaped curve. Hence to validate the hypothesis, the sign of the coefficients of FD and LnGDPC are expected to be positive, whereas negative signs are expected from the coefficient of their squared terms.

Hence, based on the signs of the parameters of FD and FDsq, GDPC and GDPCsq, the EKC can adopt different shapes which include;

- ❖ $\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_5 < 0$ and $\alpha_2, \alpha_4, \alpha_6 > 0$ = indicates a U-shaped linkage among the interested variables
- ❖ $\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_5 > 0$ and $\alpha_2, \alpha_4, \alpha_6 < 0$ = implies an inverted U-shaped relationship, known as the EKC hypothesis

- ❖ $\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_5 < 0$ and $\alpha_2, \alpha_4, \alpha_6 < 0$ or $\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_5 > 0$ and $\alpha_2, \alpha_4, \alpha_6 > 0$ = No evidence for EKC hypothesis.

3.3 Estimation Techniques

We employed cross-section ARDL technique proposed by Pesaran and Shin (1998) to investigate the financial development-environmental quality nexus while accounting for the role of institutional quality. This technique is chosen because of its advantage in tackling small sample size cases (ie. 15 nations which is less than time period). Also, the method analyses long term and short run estimates as well as taking care of forecast errors. Chudik et al. (2016) stated that the CS-ARDL estimator is most desirable where T is not too large and lies between the ranges of 30 to 50 which is the case of our study. The CS-ARDL estimate is superior to ARDL technique because it consists of a systematic type of approximations which enables the recognition of established models and components that are sequentially linked. The approach is also desirable in a situation where the variables are integrated of mixed order (I[1] and I(0)). Thus, we used various techniques such as Pesaran (2007) CIPS as well as covariate-augmented Dickey–Fuller (CADF) test for unit roots proposed by Hansen, (1995) to estimate the panel unit root to ensure reliable coefficients. Also the Westerlund (2007) cointegration test which contains possibility of cross-dependence was utilized in the establishment of long-run stabilizing linkages. With the presence of cointegration among the coefficients with cross dependence outcome, we employed the CS-ARDL method to examine the long run relationship among coefficients. To check for the robustness of long lasting stability association, we employed the Augmented Mean Group (AMG) proposed proposed by Eberhardt (2012) as well as Common Correlated Effects Mean Group Estimates (CCEMG) propounded by Pesaran (2006). Finally, the method used here takes care of heterogeneity, cross-sectional dependency, and various measurement periods’ problems.

4.0 ANALYSIS

4.1. Cross sectional dependency and Slope Homogeneity Tests

In order to overcome erroneous regression and inaccurate estimations, we carried out series of diagnostic tests including cross-sectional dependence and slope homogeneity tests. Consequently, we estimated cross-sectional dependence utilizing the Lagrangian multiplier (LM) estimation propounded by Pesaran (2015), the CD test suggested by Pesaran (2007), the LM methods by Breusch and Pagan (1980), and the slope homogeneity by Pesaran and Yamagata (2008). The former was necessitated by distinctive nature of economic policies practiced by various nations of same region and the latter was to validate the reality of homogeneity assumption. To be precise, the result is presented in table 4 and the outcome indicates evidence of interdependency among the factors (as reflected by statistical significance of the probability values of Pesaran (2015) LM, the Pesaran (2007) CDs, and the Breusch-Pagan (1980) LM tests. Also, the slope homogeneity test validated the assumption of heterogeneity (as indicated by delta and revised delta).

<i>Model</i>	<i>Pesaran (2007) CD test</i>	<i>Pesaran (2015) LM test</i>	<i>Breusch-Pagan (1980) LM test</i>	<i>Slope homogeneity test</i>		<i>P-Value</i>
<i>LCO₂ =f(FD LGDPC LGLO LURB INSTQ)</i>	536.062***	29.746***	4.856***	<i>Delta_tilde</i>	12.465***	0.000

<i>P-value</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	<i>Adj. Delta_tilde</i>	14.167***	0.000
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Hint: *, **, and *** are 10%, 5%, and 1% significant level, respectively

Source: Authors Computation, 2023, from STATA, 16.0

4.1.3 Second Generation Unit Root Test

The establishment of cross sectional dependency necessitated the adoption of second generation panel unit root test in testing for stationarity status of the variables. Hence we employed CIPS and CADF tests to ascertain whether or not series have unit root. These tests can identify heterogeneity inside and among panel dataset. The results are presented in table 5 which revealed mixed order of integration of the variables. For instance, all the variables except financial development were not stationary at levels but when differenced once, they become stationary. Financial development was stationary at levels. Thus we have mixed order such as I(1) and I(0) series.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>CIPS</i>		<i>CADF</i>	
	<i>I(0)</i>	<i>I(1)</i>	<i>I(0)</i>	<i>I(1)</i>
<i>CO₂</i>	-1.716	-5.25***	-2.059	-3.951***
<i>FD</i>	-2.972**	-5.55***	-2.640**	-4.182***
<i>LGDP</i>	-1.192	-4.977***	-1.378	-3.196***
<i>INSTQ</i>	-2.132	-5.007***	-2.002	-3.673***
<i>LGLO</i>	-0.92	-3.998***	-1.186	-2.689**
<i>LURB</i>	-1.161	-4.883***	-0.881	-3.636***

Hint: *, **, and *** are 10%, 5%, and 1% significant level, respectively

Source: Authors Computation, 2023, from STATA, 16.0

4.2 Co-integration Test

The study adopted Westerlund (2007) co-integration technique in the analysis of long run equilibrium relationship among variables. This method is a second generation co-integration which is more desirable for our data having established cross sectional dependence among countries. Thus, the result in table 6, showed that the null hypothesis of no cointegration must be rejected and as such, a long run equilibrium association exist among the variables.

<i>Statistics</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>P-value</i>
<i>Gτ</i>	1.892***	0.000
<i>Gα</i>	-4.141*	0.071
<i>Pτ</i>	-1.671***	0.000
<i>Pa</i>	2.331*	0.062

Hint: *, **, and *** are 10%, 5%, and 1% significant level, respectively

Source: Authors Computation, 2023, from STATA, 16.0

4.3 CS-ARDL for Long run and Short run Analysis

The study utilized cross-sectional auto regressive distributed lag approach in the analysis of the long run and short term relationships among the variables. The result is presented in table 7 below

and it contains two models of both long run and short run respectively. Model 1 is the estimation of dependent and independent variables without interaction term while model two involved regression with the interaction term. Results indicate that in the long run, financial development exerts negative and significant impact on carbon emission in both models. This implies that rise in FD helps to reduce pollution via carbon emission in ECOWAS within the period of study. Also, the squared term of FD has positive and significant influence on CO₂ which means that rise in FDsq triggers pollution in the region. This further supports EKC hypothesis of U-shaped association between FD and CO₂ in ECOWAS region within the period of study. Economic growth (GDPC) and its squared term showed negative and significant influence on carbon emission across the two specifications. This reveals that at the early stage of economic development, rise in economic activity increases pollution until a certain income level where it enhances the environmental quality by reducing pollution. This finding further validates the EKC hypothesis of inverted U-shape relationship for the case of ECOWAS.

Globalization and institutional quality exert negative but insignificant influence on carbon emission while urbanization has positive and insignificant impact on CO₂ in ECOWAS as seen in model 1. However, in model 2, urbanization and globalization exert positive and significant influence on carbon emission. The conditional impact of financial development on environmental quality (that is when financial development index is interacted with institutional quality index) is negative and significant at the 1% level of significant. This implies that financial development index on its own reduced environmental pollution and the interaction with financial development further enhanced the quality of the environment in ECOWAS. Finally the error correction terms for both models show that errors from short run to lung run are corrected at an adjustment speed of 79.3% and 83% yearly.

Table 7. Cross-Sectional (ARDL) Analysis Long Run and Short Run.				
	Model1		Model 2	
Variables	Long run	Short run	Long run	Short run
FD	-0.083**	-0.576	-0.194**	-0.713
	[0.554]	[0.680]	[0.687]	[0.505]
FDsq	0.466*	0.443	0.028**	0.320
	[0.545]	[1.471]	[0.679]	[0.905]
LGDPC	0.542*	0.021	0.373*	0.343
	[0.802]	[0.159]	[0.854]	[0.872]
LGDPCsq	-0.439**	-0.329	-0.517**	-0.365
	[0.670]	[0.494]	[0.598]	[0.448]
LGLO	-0.405	0.052	0.003**	-0.064
	[0.566]	[0.168]	[0.312]	[0.274]
LURB	0.159	0.218	0.349**	0.607*
	[0.482]	[0.245]	[0.459]	[0.338]
INSTQ	-0.016	-0.010		
	[0.033]	[0.025]		
FD*INSTQ			-0.201***	-0.160
			[0.366]	[0.328]
ECT		-0.793***		-0.830***
		[0.075]		[0.083]

Notes: *, **, and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level of significance respectively. Values in brackets represent standard errors.

Source: Authors Computation, 2023, from STATA, 16.0

To check the consistency of the econometric method adopted in our analysis, we employed both AMG and CCEMG methods and the results are presented in table 8. Hence, the results in table 8 are much similar with those of CS-ARDL technique. For example, FD conditional and unconditional impact has negative and significant impact on CO₂. FDsq exert positive and significant influence on pollution while GDPC and its squared term exert positive and negative impact on carbon emission respectively.

	Model 1		Model 2	
Variables	AMG	CCEMG	AMG	CCEMG
<i>FD</i>	-0.114**	-0.606**	-0.893*	0.303*
	[0.186]	[0.099]	[0.110]	[0.841]
<i>FDsq</i>	0.962*	0.932*	0.826**	0.267**
	[0.816]	[0.185]	[0.877]	[0.368]
<i>LGDP</i>	0.076**	0.001**	0.019**	-0.008**
	[0.363]	[0.018]	[0.025]	[0.022]
<i>LGDPsq</i>	0.013*	-0.034**	-0.012**	0.0369**
	[0.033]	[0.022]	[0.033]	[0.032]
<i>LGLO</i>	0.041**	-0.009	0.039	-0.042
	[0.021]	[0.050]	[0.024]	[0.040]
<i>LURB</i>	0.499**	0.074***	0.505	0.713***
	[0.195]	[0.426]	[0.192]	[0.571]
<i>INSTQ</i>	-0.002	0.027		
	[0.029]	[0.030]		
<i>FD*INSTQ</i>			-0.099*	0.095*
			[0.357]	[0.431]
OBS	465	465	465	465

Notes: *, **, and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level of significance respectively.

Values in brackets represent standard errors

Source: Authors Computation, 2023, from STATA, 16.0

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

As seen in table, financial development improves environmental quality by significantly reducing carbon emission in ECOWAS within the period of study while the squared term of FD exert positive and significant influence on CO₂. This further supports EKC hypothesis of U-shaped association between FD and CO₂ in ECOWAS region within the period under study. These findings tally with the findings of Khan and Ozturk (2021) while it contradicts the findings of Hasanet *al* (2021); Saidi and Mbarek (2017) and Dogan and Turkekul (2016) who could not find support for EKC hypothesis. The conditional impact of financial development on environmental quality (that is, when financial development index is interacted with institutional quality index) is

negative and significant at 1% level of significant. This implies that financial development index on its own reduced environmental pollution and the interaction with institutional quality further enhanced the quality of the environment in ECOWAS by further reducing carbon emission. This goes to show that financial development works better on environmental quality if institutional quality is brought to bear. Therefore, ECOWAS must not work to produce powerful leaders but instead, build string institutions so that financial development can thrive. This is because ECOWAS has had her share in leadership crises due to incompetence, lack of capacity, integrity, honesty and courage to do the right thing and shun corruption.

Economic growth (GDPC) and its squared showed positive and negative significant influence on carbon emission across the two specifications. This reveals that at the early stage of economic development, rise in economic activity increases pollution until a certain income level where it enhances environmental quality by reducing pollution. This finding further validates the EKC hypothesis of inverted U-shape relationship for the case of ECOWAS. This finding also is in tandem with the findings of Saboori et al. (2012); Ahmad et al. (2017); Haseeb *et al* (2018) etc. while the outcome contradicts the findings of Abid (2015); Mikayilov et al. (2018); and Mikayilov et al. (2018). This finding indicates that if the quest for development becomes overwhelming, environmental considerations could be jettisoned. ECOWAS sub-Region must be abreast of the fact as the quest for development increases. There is, therefore the need to balance development with sustainable environment.

Globalization and institutional quality exert negative but insignificant influence on carbon emission while urbanization has positive and insignificant impact on CO₂ in ECOWAS as seen in model 1. However, in model 2, urbanization and globalization exert positive and significant influence on carbon emission. Finally, institutional quality index on its own exert negative but insignificant impact on carbon emission and this contradicts te findings of Zakaria and Bibi (2019); Ibrahim and Law (2016); Goel, Herrala (2013) etc. who found significant linkage between CO₂ and institutional quality.

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Financial sector development enhances efficient access to financial services and products and enables the flow of funds, which drives consumption and investment, thereby increasing employment, lifting individuals out of poverty, and thus improving economic performance. It increases the magnitude of domestic savings and boosts the effectiveness of monetary policy while ensuring that scarce financial resources are channeled to the highest priority economic alternatives. Financial sector development, though associated with higher energy use and economic growth, gives households and businesses affordable and easy access to finance, which could lead to higher carbon emissions and deterioration in environmental quality. However, this present study set out to investigate if financial Development interacting with institutional quality does have significant mitigating impact on environmental degradation in ECOWAS sub-region. The conditional impact of financial development on environmental quality (that is, when financial development index is interacted with institutional quality index) is negative and significant at 1% level of significance. This implies that financial development index on its own reduced environmental pollution and the interaction with institutional quality further enhanced the quality of the environment in ECOWAS by further reducing carbon emission.

This result shows that ECOWAS strong and efficient institutions are needed to achieve sustainable environment and not strong individuals as leaders. There is therefore, need for ECOWAS to work towards entrenching or electing good leaders with the requisite capacity, competence, integrity and moral rectitude to drive and propel strong intuitions and the needed reforms. Leadership has always been the bane of Africa and once this is solved, every other issue begins to take shape.

This study, therefore, concludes that financial development matters for environmental quality and even matters more or works better if there are efficient and strong institutions. ECOWAS countries, though at different levels of income, can work towards rapid or efficient financial development because its benefits far more outweigh its cost. When interacting with institutional quality, the long run benefits of financial development will eventually lead to reduction in environmental degradation and thus lead to quality and sustainable environment.

This study has some policy implications for stakeholders in ECOWAS countries. Stakeholders and indeed policy makers in ECOWAS sub-region should pursue financial development within the limits imposed by institutional quality. Therefore, there is need to elect credible leaders who would drive reforms that will entrench institutional quality and financial development. Furthermore, policy interventions and the introduction of green financial reforms that encourage environmentally friendly projects are needed to ensure sustainable environment. Government can give tax rebate or even subsidies to industries that adopt green technologies or those that import energy-efficient technologies from advanced countries. Furthermore, increase in access to green finance to assist micro, small and medium scale enterprises will be policy decision that has the effect of reducing the impact of financial development on the environment.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions: Conceptualization: F.C.O., and B.I.U.; Methodology: F.C.O. and B.I.U.; Software: C.F.E. and V.A.I.; Validation: E.A. and V.A.I.; Formal analysis: B.I.U. and F.C.O.; Investigation: E.A., and C.F.E; Resources: F.C.A. and B.I.U.; Data curation: V.A.I, and E.A; Writing—original draft preparation: B.I.U., F.C.O. and C.F.E.; writing—review and editing: E.A., B.I.U., and F.C.O.;

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